

Collaborative Peer Review as a Strategy in Teaching Essay Writing

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Collaboration, Writing, Essay, Peer, Assessment, Review

Abstract. This action research aimed at comparing the writing performances of the students prior and after the use of the strategy “Collaborative Peer Review” or CPR in writing compositions. The study participants were enrolled in Reading and Writing Skills subject. The 293 Grade 11 respondents were further identified using cluster sampling for the quantitative data. For the qualitative data, a random sample from the respondents were selected. The main instrument used in the study were the students’ essays which were analyzed using a scoring rubric. This scoring rubric was based on the qualities of a well-written text from the Reading and Writing lesson. This was validated and checked by English language teachers. The same rubric was used for both the Pre-Test and Post-Test outputs of the respondents to ensure consistency of interpretation. From 83.85 of Satisfactory scores, the Collaborative Peer Review Strategy raised to 89.80 mean score which is interpreted as Very Satisfying Improvement. Further investigation reveals that through the Collaborative Peer Review, the feedback given by peers are helpful; reflective and critical thinking skills were tapped through guided peer review; and rewriting is the essential component of the strategy. Based on the study, peer assessment is effective since it promotes critical thinking and reflective analysis among students. Also, the guidance of the teacher is necessary in the practice of this kind of peer assessment. Above all, students are positively influenced to enhance their writing if there are comments given to their written output.

Introduction

Writing is the most complex among the macro-skills of communication. Despite it being complex, it is crucial, not only to language learning but across to different learning areas. This inspired the proponent to venture research about writing pedagogies. In senior high school curriculum, the students are expected to submit essays as proof of their achievement of certain learning competencies. Failure to show competence in writing paragraph, students may be left behind.

The proponent had a chance to do research before about students’ writing qualities in Labas Senior High School in Santa Rosa City. The findings show serious problems in the writing competence of the students, particularly the text organization, basic writing conventions, and coherence. He wanted to further this research. This time, the researcher plans to employ a called “Collaborative Peer Review” to improve students’ writing.

The proposed action is grounded by the tenets of assessment, feedback, and collaboration. Upon getting the initial writing competence of the students (pre-test), the researcher employed the said strategy. During the process of application, the writing progress were monitored until it reached the final written output which was considered as the post-test.

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Action Research Questions

This research generally aimed to improve the writing competence of the senior high school students using the researcher's Collaborative Peer Review Strategy. Specifically, the researcher sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the mean score of the students before using the Collaborative Peer Review (CPR)?
2. What is the mean score of the students after using the CPR?
3. Is there any significant difference between the pretest and post test score of the students?
4. How did the intervention strategy enhance the fundamental writing skills of the students?

Proposed Innovation, Intervention and Strategy

This action research revolved on the objective of improving the students' writing competence through systematic feedbacking, while using collaboration in both writing and checking. This rooted from students' writing competence that implied the need for the improvement of the basic writing skills. It looked at the student as a critical reader. This was a potential to be used as a strategy in assessing students' written output. Hence, this gave birth to the Collaborative Peer Review. At start, students were initially diagnosed through a writing activity. Afterwards, a series of essay writing activities were given in congruence to the curriculum guide of Reading and Writing Skills. Every time treatment group of students write essay; they were assessed by peers based on the teacher given guide. At the end of the course, the students were given a final essay writing activity. This serves as the post-test. This were compared to the pre-test to see how well the treated group of students have improved in terms of writing. This result was compared to the controlled group who were not taught with Collaborative Peer Review Strategy.

Methodology

Sources of Data

This research was conducted at Labas Senior High School, during the 2nd semester of the School Year 2022-2023. The participants of the study are the selected Grade 11 students of Labas Senior High School where the proponent is situated. The respondents of the study must be enrolled in Reading and Writing Skills. Through clustered sampling, respondents were further determined. The number of respondents is 293. These respondents were from sections Aquinas, Aristotle, Kepler, Villar, and Einstein. For the interview, a randomly selected sample were taken from the participants. They were asked several questions about the strategy used by the teacher.

Data Gathering Methods

The study sought to evaluate the writing improvement of the respondents after Collaborative Peer Review Strategy is used. Hence, the major instrument used is essay. From Pre-Test to Post-Test, writing prompts were given for students to write essay which were used for data gathering and analysis. These essays were examined through a validated rubric. The interconnected sequence of activities in this research were patterned from Dani (2014) and Alico et al. (2019) – (1) Pre-Test, (2) Strategy, and (3) Post-Test Composition. To determine the impact of the action, an unstructured interview was also conducted among the respondents.

Data Analysis Procedure

Since the main instrument used in the study were students' essays, these were analyzed using a scoring rubric. This academic discourse was examined using the validated scoring rubric. As this used a scoring rubric, quantitative data in the form of scores were the primary data. These were presented through a table, using appropriate statistical tools. Using the t-Test for Paired Samples, the significant difference between students' pre-test and post-test writing qualities were determined.

An interview was conducted after the post-test. After conducting all the interviews, the researcher proceeded to probing questions by going through the data from the interview transcriptions. Significant statements on how participants experience and perceive the use of the Collaborative Peer Review Strategy in the remediation program were highlighted. With this, the researcher developed a cluster of meaning from these significant statements which were then used to write

descriptions of what the participants experienced and perceived about the proposed strategy. These clusters of meanings were written into themes.

It is through determining the themes that the feedback of the respondents was identified. The researcher communicated with the participants again to verify the synthesis of their responses. This step was undertaken so that participants themselves could clarify and rectify their responses; hence, the validity of the feedback was then obtained and credibility was strengthened.

Results and Discussion

Comparison of Pre Test and Post Test

Table 1 exhibits the comparison of Pre-Test and Post-Test results using the Collaborative Peer Review Strategy in writing essays. It can be observed that all sections have increased their mean scores from the Pretest to the Post-Test with the use of the Collaborative Peer Review assessment. From 83.85 of Satisfactory scores, the CPR led to the 89.80 mean score which is interpreted as Very Satisfying Improvement.

Sections	Pre-Test	Reading	Post-Test	Reading
A	78.29	Fair	85.50	Satisfying Improvement
B	81.37	Fair	86.70	Satisfying Improvement
C	81.71	Fair	87.42	Satisfying Improvement
D	84.83	Satisfactory	91.33	Very Satisfying Improvement
E	93.06	Very Satisfactory	98.06	Outstanding Improvement
Grand Mean	83.85	Satisfactory	89.80	Very Satisfying Improvement

Table No. 1 Comparison of Pre Test and Post Test

To check the reliability of the interpretation three statistical tools were used:

1. Wilcoxon Test is non-parametric tool used because the data is non-normal. In this tool, it was found that there is a significant difference observed in all groups as medians are less than p value of 0.05.
2. Kruskal - Wallis Test for Equal Medians revealed that p value of 0.0003813 is less than 0.05. Therefore, significant difference is observed between groups.
3. Mann-Whitney Post hoc also found statistical significance between groups as such p values are less than 0.05.

Based on the conducted interview among selected students, the following themes were identified: (1) the feedback given by peers are helpful; (2) aside from the improvement of writing skills, reflective and critical thinking skills were tapped through guided peer review; and (3) rewriting is the essential component of the CPR strategy.

Conclusion and Implications

This study concludes that peer assessment are effective tools to promote critical thinking and reflective analysis among students. Also, teachers' guidance is still crucial in the practice of peer assessment. Lastly, students are motivated to enhance their writing if there are comments given to their written output.

Corollary to the findings and conclusions, other teachers may also consider using the Collaborative Peer Review as a strategy in assessing essays and other written outputs. This strategy may be endorsed to other teachers as a strategy in enhancing the writing skills of the students through collaborative expertise or relevant research presentations. The future researchers

may use this study as a basis for future references / study and explore more the limitations and other problems of this study to have effective and efficient application to their specific context requirement.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in this research can be accessed through a formal request to the author of the study.

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Appendices

No appendices are included in this article.